

ISSN 2120-4160

VOL 6 | SPECIAL ISSUE 4 | FEB 2018

UGC Approved Journal Number: 44120

Shanlax International Journal of Commerce

A Peer-Reviewed, Refereed Scholarly Quarterly Journal
Globally Indexed with Impact Factor

Special Issue On

MODERN BANKING SERVICES Opportunities and Challenges

Organized by

POST GRADUATE AND RESEARCH DEPARTMENT OF COMMERCE
GOVERNMENT ARTS COLLEGE FOR MEN (Autonomous)
NAAC Accredited, Nandanam, Chennai - 600 035

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A CONCEPTUAL STUDY ON GROWTH AND IMPACT OF INTERNET BANKING AND TECHNOLOGY IN INDIAN BANKS

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Abstract

The Internet Banking is changing the banking industry and is having the major effects on banking relationships. Internet Banking involves delivery of banking products and services. This paper describes the current state of Internet banking in India and discusses its implications for the Indian banking industry. This research paper focuses on the impact of internet banking and technology in Indian banking sector. Without information technology and communication we cannot think about the success of banking industry. This paper identifies the weaknesses of conventional banking and explores the consumer awareness, use patterns, satisfaction and preferences for Internet banking and also highlights the factors that may affect the bank's strategy to adopt Internet banking.

Keywords: Internet banking, latest technology, impact, growth, Indian banks.

Introduction

Internet Banking refers to the banking services provided by the banks over the internet. Some of these services include paying of bills, funds transfer, viewing account statement, etc. Banks also deliver their latest products and services over the internet. Internet banking is performed through a computer system or similar devices that can connect to the banking site via the internet. Nowadays, you can also use internet banking on your mobile phones using a Wi-Fi or 3G connection. With the ease of availability of cyber cafes in the cities, it has become quite popular. Banking is now no more limited in going and visiting the bank in person for various purposes like depositing and withdrawing money, requesting for account statement, stop a payment, etc.

Services of Internet Banking

Banks in India are offering wide range of their services and their products through internet banking. Some of the major services and products in India are:

- Provides account statement (account info), Balance enquiry, balance statement and transaction reports used.
- Transfer funds between accounts, even if they are in different branches or cities.
- Banks Bill Payment is the easiest way to manage bills. Account holder can pay their regular monthly bills i.e. telephone, electricity, mobile phone, insurance etc. at anytime, anywhere for free. Saves time and effort.
- Can electronically submit a request for Cheque-book, Stop payment instructions, Opening a fixed deposit, Opening a recurring deposit, Intimate for the loss of ATM card etc.
- Demat is commonly used abbreviation of "Dematerialisation", which is a process whereby securities like share, debentures are converted from the material (paper documents) into electronic data and stored in the computer of an electronic Depository.

One Day State Level Seminar on **MORDEN BANKING SERVICES** *Opportunities and Challenges*

Review of Literature

Balwinder Singh and Pooja Malhotra (2014) This paper concluded that, by the end of first quarter, 2004, differences between Internet and non-Internet banks had begun to emerge in funding, in sources of income and expenditures and in measures of performance.

Vikas Chauhan and vipin Choudhary (2015) The present paper attempts to understand the concept of internet banking as well as study the benefit of internet banking from perspective of consumers as Well as banks. Further, this paper discusses the challenges and opportunities associated with the internet banking in Indian context.

Objectives of the Study

- To Study the impact of internet banking
- To analyze the impact of IT in Indian banking industry.
- To assess various aspects of IT services provided by Indian banks.

Research Methodology

The present study is based on the secondary data collected from different journals, magazines, sites and published data from various issues of RBI and different Public sector banks. Various studies on this subject have also been referred in this study.

Benefits of Internet Banking In India

1. **Easy to Set-up:** Internet banking permits to easily set up your online accounts with only prior bank account information. You can use your computer or even smart phones for creating your online accounts.
2. **Secure:** Online banking allows you to conduct your bank transactions safely and securely. You can monitor and keep track of all your financial transactions and make sure your balance information is correct.
3. **Convenience:** Internet banking gives you a platform for paying your electric bills, telephone bills and transfer funds. Making transactions right from your door step or offices are easy with single payments or recurring payments.
4. **Services:** Internet banking acts as a great medium for the banks to endorse their products and services. These services include financial planning, investment options, loan calculators and many others as simple applications on the bank's website. All these services are available 24/7.
5. **Cost-Effective:** Administrative and paper related works which occupies not only office spaces but as well creates job opportunities have been cut down with the introduction of internet banking.

Recent it Trends of Indian Banks

Today, technology is not only changing the environment but also the relationship with customers. This has brought customer relationship into greater focus.

Electronic Payment and Settlement System: The most common media of receipts and payment through banks are negotiable instruments like cheques.

Automated Teller Machine (ATM): ATMs were introduced to the Indian banking industry in the early 1990s initiated by foreign banks. It is perhaps most revolutionary aspect of virtual banking.

Phone Banking: Customers can now dial up the banks designed telephone number and he by dialing his ID number will be able to get connectivity to bank's designated computer

Internet Banking: Internet banking enables a customer to do banking transactions through the bank's website on the Internet

Mobile Banking; Mobile banking services are provided to the customers having the credit card accounts with bank.

Summary and Conclusion

Internet banking requires that the banks' internal systems to be linked with the systems in public domain. Internet Banking is susceptible to risks in the form of criminal activities, such as fraud, money laundering, tax evasion etc. Internet banking allows the banks as well as customers to operate with geographical boundaries thus creating a problem of exchange controls. Reserve Bank of India has come out with Internet banking related guidelines. Thus Internet banking has become a necessary survival weapon and is fundamentally changing the banking industry worldwide.

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